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Influence Of Human Resource Practices On Management Of Public Universities In North Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of human resource practices on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 14,305 staff from 14 public universities in North Central Nigeria. A sample of 429 staff was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection process. A 35-item structured four-point rating scale questionnaire titled “Human Resource Practices and Management Questionnaire (HRPMQ)” with over all reliability coefficient of 0.85 was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management in the Department of Educational Foundations and one in Mathematics Education in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in Faculty of Education Benue state University Makurdi. Data collected from the field were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions and Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of-fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicated that training and career planning practices have significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. It was concluded that human resource practices have significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. It was recommended among others that Government and private’s proprietors of universities should as a matter of priority undertake an in-depth assessment of their staff in order to training them in their areas of specialization through sponsoring them or organizing conference, seminars and workshops for them so that it would not only lead to increase in skills and knowledge among them but enhance maximum performance in their assigned tasks.

Keywords: human resource practices, management, training, career planning practices

INTRODUCTION

Management of public universities has in recent times seemed to be faced with an increasing competition in rapidly changing environment characterized by advancement in information technologies, globalization, deregulation and continuous public demands for quality university education. Also, the global demand for effective management of public universities seems to heighten significantly due to growing students’ populations, limited resources and the need for universities to compete in a knowledge-driven global economy. While other nations such as United States of America, Germany, Great Britain and Canada may be experiencing effective management of public universities. While African countries

such as Kenya, Ivory Coast, Burkina Faso and Nigeria are facing the challenge of ineffective management of public universities related to issues of inadequate planning, organizing, coordinating, poor commanding, inconsistent assigning of university activities to staff and students, not properly issuing instruction and guideline for universities activities to be performed, poor monitoring and evaluation of university progress of activities as well as not taking corrective measures to ensuring university objectives are achieved. Other challenging areas of management includes: funding, quality assurance, resource provision, ineffective staff performance and low productivity (Materu, 2017). These challenges may appear to have negative influence on management of public universities which in turn may reduce the quality of teaching, research and community development in Nigeria especially in North Central Nigeria.

Management is the process of achieving organizational goals through the coordinated performance of five specific functions, namely; planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling (Ukpai, 2013). Management of public universities is an approach directed at harnessing the human and material resources for the purpose of achievement university goals and objective in an efficient manner (Ukpai, 2013). It may also be seen as the organizational and administrative practice used to operate public universities. Bua (2020) maintains that it involves decision-making structures, policies and practices that govern the university's financial, academic and administrative affairs. Effective management of public universities is crucial because it impacts the quality of education, research output, resource allocation and overall institutional success (Yawe & Ivagher, 2016). When there is ineffective management, organizations hardly achieve their mandates. This means that achieving mandates of public universities in Nigeria as outlined in the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic Nigeria (FRN), 2014), such as promoting quality teaching, research and community development could be possible through appropriate human resource practices.

Human resources include academic and non-academic staff of universities (Olorunfemi, 2020). Olorunfemi further states that they are living and active input that that operates the other factors of production. According to Ogwuche (2016), human resource is those engaged in an organized setting to undertake assignments and work by schedules and jurisdictions towards an expected end. On the other hand, human resource practices involve the policies and practices applied in dealing with human resources of an organization (Robinson & Lee, 2021).

For human resources of an organization to put in their best to achieve maximum result, human resource managers must adopt appropriate human resource practices (Olorunfemi, 2020). According to Robinson and Lee (2021, p.213), there are a number of human resource practices which include recruitment and selection practices, placement practices, training practices, promotion practices, employee relations practices, performance management practices, reward management, grievance procedure and pension or social security. Smith and Davis (2017) also identify human resource practices as recruitment practices, selection practices, training, career planning, employee relations and diversity inclusion practices. This study is focused on training and career planning practices as specific variables of the study.

Training practice is an essential aspect of human resource practices. It is the process of providing educational staff with necessary skills and competences to function effectively on the job (Olorunfemi, 2020). Training is carried out either on-the-job or off-the-job such that employees may acquire new knowledge and skills while on the job or off the job. Bua and Ada (2018) opine that training can be given to university staff through conferences, workshops, seminars, mentoring and coaching. Proper training provides university staff with requisite skills for effective performance which may enhance management of the universities. This is because there would speedy execution of task and with expectation and standard by qualified staff. However, inadequate training may lead to inadequate skills among staff and in such situation, the management of public universities may be negatively affected. Providing staff with adequate training promote effective management of public universities. Such practice may not be enough for the staff hence there will be the need to provide another opportunity for career planning of the staff.

Career planning practice is a step-by-step process through which one sets his or her career goals and prepares an actionable plan to realize and achieve them. It is the process of goal identification and formulation of the path to follow to ensure every goal is fulfilled (Leigh & Blakely, 2016). Its main role is

to effectively assist the employees of an organization to archive a specific goal. Assessing employees and correct career planning may effectively motivate the employee's ability to perform their work. If there is lack of career planning, staff may not be able effectively delivery their mandate in public universities making it difficult for universities to achieve their set goals. According to Kerzener and Kerzner (2017), career planning enables individual to deliver on their mandate at their work station however, where this is lacking, the organization would stand to lose its productivity. With effective career planning, university staff are guided towards a successful and fulfilling professional life and this may impact positively on management of public universities. Also, adequate career planning could result of increasing employee relations in universities.

Ideally, no university can highly achieve its goals when the human resources practices are not well managed to put in their best potential to performing various duties. The perceived negative relationship between human resource practices and management of public universities in North Central Nigeria calls the for the need to investigate influence of human resource practices on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria with regards to variables such as training and career planning practices.

Statement of Problem

Management of public universities is significant for the actualization of national and sustainable development through the fulfillment of tripartite mandates of universities which are promotion of teaching, research and community services. However, the management of public universities in North Central Nigeria seems to face significant challenges which may be as a result of ineffective human resource practices. Despite the critical role of human resource practices in enhancing institutional performance, there are concerns efficiency in management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. Observation by the researcher and relevant educational stakeholders such as university vice chancellors, human resource managers, academic and non-academic staff seems to indicate that there is a disconnection between human resource practices and optimal university management. This disconnection may manifest in ineffective training and career planning practices.

As public universities strive to maintain competitiveness, ensure quality education, and retain top talent, the relationship between human resources practices and management becomes critical. It seems that the process of training using various platforms such conferences, workshop, seminars and mentoring appears not to be providing staff with relevant skills to perform effectively to enhance management of public universities. The issue of career planning also seems to heighten concern by the researcher and relevant stakeholders since many staff seem to fail in fulfilling their personal and institutional mandates in many public universities in North Central Nigeria. The researcher seems to blame career planning and employee relations in these universities. This is perceived to be negatively affecting management public universities. It is based on this concern that the researcher seeks to investigate relationship between human resource practices and management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of human resource practices on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of training practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the influence of career planning practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of training practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of career planning practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Training practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.
2. Career planning practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 14,305 staff from 14 public universities in North Central Nigeria. A sample of 429 staff was used for the study. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection process. A 35-item structured four-point rating scale questionnaire titled “Human Resource Practices and Management Questionnaire (HRPMQ)” with over all reliability coefficient of 0.85 was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management in the Department of Educational Foundations and one in Mathematics Education in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, all in Faculty of Education Benue state University Makurdi. The instrument was designed on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA=4), Agreed (A=3), Disagreed (D=2) and Strongly Disagreed (SD=1). Data collected from the field were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions and Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of-fit was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented, analyzed and interpreted as follows:

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of training practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria?*

The data that provided answer to the research question is presented on Table 1.

Table 1. Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the Influence of Training Practice on Management of Public Universities in North Central Nigeria

No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	Decision
1	Training helps to improve staff capacity which is geared towards advancing their responsibilities in accomplishing the university’s objectives.	408	182	165	37	24	3.24	0.85	Agree
2	When staff are given the opportunities to attend conferences, their knowledge is increased towards maximum performance in their assigned task.	408	207	159	23	19	3.36	0.79	Agree
3	Quality instruction is enhanced among when workshops are organized for staff.	408	200	141	38	29	3.25	0.90	Agree
4	University staff learn better methods of handling examinations when given the opportunity to attend seminars.	408	193	94	53	68	3.00	1.13	Agree
5	Proper staff training helps in the actualization of universities objectives with ease.	408	203	105	56	44	3.14	1.02	Agree
	Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation						3.20	0.94	Agree

Source: Field Study 2025

Table 1 shows that items 11-15 had mean scores of 3.24, 3.36, 3.25, 3.00 and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.85, 0.79, 0.90, 1.13 and 1.02 respectively. Based on the criteria for decision-making, it means that the mean scores for all the items were rated above the cut-off point of 2.50. This means that respondents agreed that training helps to improve staff capacity which is geared towards advancing their responsibilities in accomplishing the university's objectives. They indicated that when staff are given the opportunities to attend conferences, their knowledge is increased towards maximum performance in their assigned task. They maintained that quality instruction is enhanced among when workshops are organized for staff. Furthermore, they responded that university staff learn better methods of handling examinations when given the opportunity to attend seminars. In addition, they indicated that proper staff training helps in the actualization of universities objectives with ease. The cluster mean of 3.20 was also above the cut-off point of 2.50. The standard deviations are small which shows that there is homogeneity in respondents' responses for the items raised. This implies that training practice has positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of career planning practice on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria?*

The data that provided answer to the research question are presented on Table 2.

Table 2. Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the Influence of Career Planning Practice on Management of Public Universities in North Central Nigeria

No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Proper career planning enhances employee's ability to perform their work effectively.	408	237	121	27	23	3.40	0.84	Agree
7	Career planning is helpful in matching university's objectives.	408	219	141	31	17	3.38	0.80	Agree
8	Quality assurance is enhanced in the university through proper career training of staff.	408	170	162	41	35	3.11	0.93	Agree
9	Universities find it difficult to determine staff potentials for better output without career training.	408	141	134	55	78	2.81	1.12	Agree
10	University's growth is better enhanced through career training of staff.	408	168	175	36	29	3.09	0.94	Agree
	Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation						3.16	0.92	Agree

Source: *Field Study 2025*

Table 2 reveals that items 16-20 had mean scores of 3.40, 3.38, 3.11, 2.81 and 3.09 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.84, 0.80, 0.93, 1.12 and 0.94 respectively. Based on the criteria for decision-making, it means that the mean scores for all the items were rated above the cut-off point of 2.50. This means that respondents indicated proper career planning enhances employee's ability to perform their work effectively. They indicated that career planning is helpful in matching university's objectives. They agreed that quality assurance is enhanced in the university through proper career training of staff. Furthermore, they responded that agreed that universities find it difficult to determine staff potentials for better output without career training. Moreover, they agreed that university's growth is better enhanced through career training of staff. The cluster mean of 3.03 was also above the cut-off point of 2.50. The standard deviations are small. This shows that career planning practice has positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

In order to test the seven hypotheses of this study, the chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit was used to test the options of respondents at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Training practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria

Table 3. Chi-square test of the Influence of Training Practice on Management of Public Universities in North Central Nigeria

Opinions	Observed N	Expected N	Level of Sig.	df	χ^2	P-value	Decision
SA	37	102.0	0.05	3	214.29	0.00	Sig.
A	41	102.0					
D	133	102.0					
SD	197	102.0					

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 102.0.

Table 3 reveals that $\chi^2 = 214.29$; $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis which states that training practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. The implication is that training practice has significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Planning practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

Table 4. Chi-square test of the Influence of Planning Practice on Management of Public Universities in North Central Nigeria

Opinions	Observed N	Expected N	Level of Sig.	df	χ^2	P-value	Decision
SA	36	102.0	0.05	3	241.49	0.00	Sig.
A	38	102.0					
D	147	102.0					
SD	187	102.0					

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 102.0.

Table 4 shows that $\chi^2 = 241.49$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since p-value of $0.00 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis which states that planning practice has no significant influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria was therefore, rejected. This implies that planning practice has significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding revealed that training practice has significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. This indicates that training helps to improve staff capacity which is geared towards advancing their responsibilities in accomplishing the university's objectives. When staff are given the opportunities to attend conferences, their knowledge is increased towards maximum performance in their assigned task. Quality instruction is enhanced among when workshops are organized for staff. University staff learn better methods of handling examinations when given the opportunity to attend seminars. Proper staff training helps in the actualization of universities objectives with ease. The finding is also related to that of Ojoh and Okoh (2015) which showed that training has positive impact on organizational performance. The finding is also in agreement with that of Godwin, Adeniran and Jamogha (2020) which showed positive significant influence of training and development on the performance of staff of the selected university libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

The second finding of this study revealed that career planning practice has significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. This indicated that proper career planning enhances employee's ability to perform their work effectively. Career planning is helpful in matching university's objectives. Quality assurance is enhanced in the university through proper career training of staff. Universities find it difficult to determine staff potentials for better output without career training. University's growth is better enhanced through career training of staff. The finding corroborates with that of Mwashila, Idua and Kazungu (2017) which revealed that career planning had a positive significant influence on management of public universities in Coast region of Kenya. Further, the universities under study had programmes that developed their academic staff for future positions, formulated self-assessment tools that helped their academic staff understand their career aspirations and had career succession plans. The findings also showed that career advancement had a positive significant influence on academic staff performance in Kenyan public universities in Coast region. The finding is also in line with that of Olusola (2016) which revealed that there is positive significant relationship of career planning and career management with career development of employees in Nigerian Banks in Ogun State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was established that training and career planning practices have significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria. It was concluded that human resource practices have significant positive influence on management of public universities in North Central Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and private's proprietors of universities should as a matter of priority undertake an in-depth assessment of their staff in order to training them in their areas of specialization through sponsoring them or organizing conference, seminars and workshops for them so that it would not only lead to increase in skills and knowledge among them but enhance maximum performance in their assigned tasks.
2. University management should intensify career planning practices such as setting of goals and objectives through personal development plan, appraisal and development reviews, development programmes and work experiences with proper guidance so as to improve staff satisfaction, utilize their skills and knowledge as well as get them fully motivated to achieve maximum performance.

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